

The Future of Reactor Physics: A Need for Experiments

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ABSTRACT

Reactor physics relies fundamentally on experiments: to validate models, qualify materials, support fuel-cycle innovation, and educate the next generation of nuclear professionals. Yet the global decline of zero-power and specialized research reactors has created structural gaps that now limit validation capabilities across thermal and fast-spectrum systems. Structures such as OECD NEA Working Parties are organized around specialties, which while relevant in many ways, limit the discussion of societal choices and goals attached to priorities. This paper reviews experimental needs for reactor physics from three complementary perspectives: (1) life-extension of existing reactors, (2) fuel-cycle closure and advanced systems, and (3) new reactor concepts including fast-spectrum, molten-salt, and high-temperature technologies. A fourth cross-cutting dimension, education and training, is included due to its essential role in sustaining operational and research competence. For each application domain, high-value experimental areas are identified and classified as optimization, enabling, or transformative, with representative metrics drawn from benchmark projects (IRPhEP, ICSBEP), IAEA TECDOCs, and reports from NEA Working Parties, including WPEC, WPNCS, and WPRS. The analysis highlights recurring limitations: the lack of clean integral fast-spectrum benchmarks; insufficient high-burnup post-irradiation examination (PIE) coupled with well-characterized irradiation conditions; limited access to multiphysics coupled experiments; and declining student and professional access to hands-on reactor operations. Addressing these needs requires a diversified experimental landscape, including university-scale facilities and national-laboratory-level platforms. In this context, the concept of a fast-spectrum, zero-power educational and research reactor is motivated as an opportunity in Switzerland. This work aims to support coherent planning of experimental infrastructures aligned with societal imperatives, scientific priorities, and long-term workforce sustainability.

Keywords: reactor physics, experimental validation, fast spectrum, fuel-cycle closure, zero-power reactors, education

1. INTRODUCTION – A BIT OF EPISTEMOLOGY

At first glance, a zero-power research reactor such as CROCUS at EPFL and a full-scale European Pressurized Reactor (EPR) might seem worlds apart: one serves purely fundamental reactor physics education and measurements, while the other produces gigawatt-scale electricity. Yet both obey the same neutron-transport equations, differing only in scale. Similarly, a U.S.-designed APR-1000 and a Russian VVER-1000 share core physics and pressure-vessel PWR technology, despite differences in fuel assembly geometry, control-rod mechanisms, and safety philosophies.

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However, as Jacques Ellul observed in *The Technological Society*, technical choices are not neutral: they carry social, political and diplomatic weight [1]. Installing a VVER in Iran carries different implications than deploying a Westinghouse PWR in Switzerland; not because of physics, but because of the socio-technical system it belongs to, including fuel-supply agreements, regulatory regimes, and geopolitical alignments. This illustrates that “technology is not neutral”; it both shapes and is shaped by the society in which it is embedded.

Research agendas reflect a similar multiplicity of motivations. They arise from scientific curiosity of individuals or communities, industrial priorities, regulatory pressures, and international collaborations. Community-level efforts, such as WPEC’s High-Priority Request List (HPRL), or WPNC’s Criticality Safety priority list, synthesize hundreds of expert inputs to identify the most urgent nuclear-data gaps [2]–[4]. At the same time, the WPRS-convened Zero Power Reactor (ZPR) Task Force has warned that the global decline in zero-power reactors threatens the ability to validate new core concepts [5]. In parallel, Europe anticipates the need to train tens of thousands of new professionals across the nuclear sector in the next decade, from technicians to scientists, a goal simulations alone cannot meet.

Thus, the question becomes: *which experiments do we need, for what purpose, and whom do they empower?* Beyond achieving specific accuracies (e.g., sub-0.05% k_{eff} , 1-2% flux-map precision), experiments must be aligned with application context. Are we targeting life extension of existing fleets to meet IPCC climate-mitigation pathways [6]–[8]? Or enabling closed fuel cycles to advance the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals on responsible consumption and clean energy [9], [10]? Drawing on Schumacher’s concept of “appropriate technology,” and Illich’s “convivial tools” framework, we should favor experimental approaches that are locally adaptable, democratically governed, and empowering; for instance, small-scale facilities where students, researchers, and stakeholders collaborate on shared goals [11], [12].

This paper moves beyond field-by-field wish lists to examine application-driven experimental needs across existing-reactor life extension, fuel-cycle closure, and novel-design validation. It discusses and charts a coherent strategy for reactor-physics research integrating scientific rigor, societal imperatives, and the critical task of workforce development. For concision purposes, not all experiments are discussed in detail, but as a whole topic by topic, with appropriate tables for providing more details.

2. NEEDS AND APPLICATIONS

The field is primarily application-driven, which leads us to differentiate the needs for new experiments in two ways. First, the classification “O/E/T” proposed here draws on technology assessment frameworks used in innovation studies, adapted to the specific context of reactor physics validation needs:

- **optimization (O):** making things slightly better, incremental or supportive, for keeping systems safe and cost-effective. In this category falls for instance the modelling of temperature effects (Doppler, moderator, voids) or vessel fluence for refined safety margins.
- **enabling (E):** making things possible, for vital but currently limited operation, such as allowing for denser fuel storage, transitioning to MOX fuels, or nuclear data for new systems.
- **transformative (T):** changing the game, expand current capabilities, such as benchmark data allowing for transmutation systems and burners, thus reducing waste or closing the fuel-cycle.

The second classification is related to the goal application. In this matter, four topics are differentiated: life-extension of existing reactors; fuel-cycle closure; new reactor designs; education and training.

2.1. Life-extension of existing reactors

Life-extension decisions are fundamentally data-driven: regulators and plant operators must demonstrate that cores operating beyond their originally licensed burnup or service life continue to meet safety and performance requirements [13]–[15]. That requires closing the validation loop between depletion predictions, measured integral reactivity behavior, and the long-term reliability of in-core and ex-core instrumentation and structures under aged-core conditions. Long term operation (LTO) therefore encompasses two intertwined neutronics areas: (a) high-burnup fuel behavior (both in-core, and in storage post-irradiation), and (b) changes in the neutron flux and fluence experienced by aging reactor systems, including core internals and the pressure vessel.

Practically, the highest and most immediate leverage is provided by high-burnup irradiation campaigns in material testing reactors, combined with detailed post-irradiation examination (PIE), as well as burnup-credit integral benchmarks. These experiments directly support denser, safer storage and validated fuel-management strategies, thus lowering repository load and costs.

Complementary experiments, such as flux mapping, reactivity-coefficients, and kinetics/pulse tests, ensure that neutronics models remain accurate when small spectral or material changes (e.g., crud buildup, cladding corrosion, fission-product poisoning) occur over long operation. In parallel, fast-neutron dosimetry and spectral-prediction improvements contribute to the assessment of fluence on the reactor pressure vessel and other aging structures, a key requirement for long-term operation. Finally, detector validation secures trustworthy online monitoring, a prerequisite for any extended operation.

The main and direct interest of these actions and experiments is twofold. First, they are generally accessible, relying largely on existing research reactors and established measurement techniques. Second, they reduce regulatory uncertainty, support cost-effective lifetime extension, and directly contribute to climate goals by keeping low-carbon capacity on an acceptable timescale [6].

Table I. Non-exhaustive list of experiments for life-extension applications. Tiers: optimizing, enabling, transformative. Difficulty: low, medium, high, very high. Bold: reactor facility required. [14]–[23]

Experiments	Purpose / Application	Typical Facilities	Target metrics (examples)	Tier	Diff.
High-burnup irradiation + PIE	Validate depletion and isotopics at high burnup, and burnup-credit (stor./transp.)	Material testing reactor (BR2, ATR, HFR) + hot-cells for PIE	Actinide assay unc. ~2-3%; benchmarked depletion trends	E	M/H
Flux & reaction-rate map. (EOL)	Validate power peaking & spectrum at EOL	Instrumented loops in RR; ZPR mock-ups	Local flux error <1%; Pin-by-pin react. rates ±1-2%	O/E	M
Burnup-credit integral exp.	Validate burnup-credit for storage/transport licensing	Sub/critical assemblies (spent fuel/surrogates)	k_{eff} unc. <0.5% Validated spectral indices	E	H
Reactivity coefficient & Doppler/void	Validate reactivity coefficients under aged-core conditions	Zero-power rigs, dedicated loops, small test assemblies	Doppler coefficient ±5-10 pcm/°C; Moderator coeff. unc. within licensing	O/E	M
Kinetics & transient pulse	Validate transient response of aged cores	Pulse exp. (TRIGA), ZPR tests [24]–[26]	β_{eff} , Λ to ±3-5%; transient flux shapes with μ s timing	E	L
Instrumentation & detector ageing tests	Ensure in-core monitors remain accurate at high burnup and altered core	Pulsed/steady test reactors, detector calibration labs	Det. response function ±2% over operating range; dead-time/linearity tests	O/E	M
TH boundary for aging cores	Support coupled neutronics/T-H validation	PKL, ATLAS, other integral loops	T°/press. time series with sensor accuracy (PKL)	O	M
Dosimetry and nuclear data for RPV	Validate RPV embrittlement models and support LTO up to 60-80 years	ZPR, RR and NPP data; activation labs; hot cells [27]–[29]	Fluence unc. ≤10% (1 MeV-eq); experiments for steel nuclear data	E	M

2.2. Fuel-cycle closure

Fuel-cycle closure relies primarily on fast-spectrum reactors, e.g. sodium fast reactors (SFR), for transmutation and advanced fuel cycles. Experimentation spans the entire chain from fuel fabrication (including plutonium- and minor-actinide-bearing fuels), to irradiation testing, chemical separation processes, accelerator-driven systems, high-precision nuclear data, and finally waste-form performance. It demands experimental validation that goes far beyond small parameter tuning: it defines whether multi-recycling and minor-actinide (MA) transmutation are feasible at all. This includes:

- Optimizing & validating experiments include coupled cycle simulations, and decay-heat/delayed-neutron data. Those are critical for efficiency and safety margins.
- Enabling experiments, includes integral fast-spectrum benchmarks, actinide cross-sections, and PIE campaigns. Without these, closed-cycle neutronics cannot be qualified.
- A specific tier concerns strategic demonstrations of accelerator-driven (ADS) and molten-loop systems. Although they are exploratory, they have transformative potential for waste minimization and hybrid systems.

The overall difficulty is high, due to radiotoxic materials, complex infrastructure, and international licensing. This application area is the most infrastructure-intensive and facility-limited among all NEA Working Party domains. However, the societal impact is transformative, as these experiments determine whether sustainable fuel recycling and waste minimization are realistic, addressing long-term energy independence and intergenerational equity.

Table II. Non-exhaustive list of experiments for fuel-cycle closure. Tiers: optimizing, enabling, transformative. Difficulty: low, medium, high, very high. Bold: reactor facility required. [18], [30]–[40]

Experiment / Facility Type	Purpose / Application	Target metric (examples)	Tier	Diff.
MA and high-MA content fuel irradiation (e.g., ATR, HFIR, JHR)	Validate MA transmutation fuel performance in SFR/ADS	Typical burnup 5-20% FIMA with dim. change unc. $\leq 3\%$	E/T	VH
MA-bearing fuel fabrication experiments	Industrial feasibility of U-MA, U-Pu-MA MOX	Pu+MA homogeneity $\leq 3\%$ deviation across batches (JAEA)	E	H
Pyroprocessing electrorefining tests (hot-cell scale)	Validate actinide recovery efficiencies; waste minimization	TRU recovery $\geq 99\%$, lanth. contamination $\leq 0.5\text{-}1\%$ in metal product (Korea/US)	E/T	VH
Aqueous reprocessing (PUREX/UREX/GANEX) hot-cell campaigns	Close fuel cycle through advanced solvent extraction	Separation factors $10^6\text{-}10^7$ for U/Pu, Am/Cm separation $> 99\%$ (GANEX)	E	VH
Decay-heat meas. (calorimeters) for MA and fission products	Needed for storage, transport, and recycling of high-MA fuels	$< 3\%$ over 0-100 years cooling time (WPEC Subgroup 40 / SG46)	E	H
Fission-product yields (FPY) for fast spectra	Needed for transmutation inventories and decay-heat	Uncertainty $\leq 2\text{-}5\%$ for major FPYs (ICSBEP)	E	M
Integral fast-reactor MA transmutation assemblies (BFS)	Validate transmutation pathways (k_{eff} & reaction rates)	k_{eff} unc. ≤ 300 pcm (IRPhEP)	E/T	VH
ADS sub. experiments (YALINA, GUINEVERE/ GENEPI-3C)	Validate source-driven subcrit. monitoring for MA fuel systems	Subcrit. unc. $\leq 0.5\%$ (500 pcm) beam-driven conditions (FREYA)	E/T	H
Cladding/wrapper irradi. for high-burnup MA fuels (HT9, ODS)	Needed for 150-200 GWd/t fuel cycles	Swelling/radiation damage unc. $\leq 5\%$ is typical in ATR/HFIR results	E	M
Waste-form durability exp. (glass, ceramic, metallic)	Long-term safety assessment for HLW repositories	Leach rate quantification unc. $\leq 10\%$ (per IAEA SRP standards)	E	M
Thermochem. of molten salts and liq. metals (U-Pu-MA-Zr, LiCl-KCl, Na)	Inputs to recycling plant design, pyroprocessing chemical modelling	No design target; typical unc. 1-2% in calorimetry and activity measurements	O/E	M

2.3. New reactor designs

Validation of new reactor designs requires primarily an enabling class of experiments. Without them, the licensing and deployment of small modular reactors (SMRs), Gen-IV systems, and hybrid reactors cannot proceed. In many respects, these validation needs overlap with those of fuel-cycle closure, but they also extend to a broader challenge: opening new technological, operational, and industrial avenues. Three functional layers can be distinguished:

- Foundational physics validation: zero-power reactor mock-ups, spectral characterization, reactivity coefficients. These directly underpin licensing and model validation.
- Multiphysics and dynamic behavior: transient, coupled core-structure, and circulation experiments bridge steady-state neutronics to realistic operations.
- System integration and shielding: ensure deployability, maintainability, and occupational safety in modular or advanced layouts.

The difficulty of these experiments ranges from moderate—such as kinetics tests and ZPR mock-ups—to very high for molten-salt, sodium, lead, or transient test loops where material compatibility, instrumentation, and safety constraints become challenging. Their societal impact is strategic: these experiments determine whether novel, inherently safe, load-flexible reactor concepts can be demonstrated, supporting long-term decarbonization, energy-security, and waste-minimization objectives.

Innovative reactor concepts (SMRs, high-temperature gas, molten-salt, lead-cooled, etc.) lack accessible, usable, useful legacy data. Each concept requires tailored integral experiments to validate neutronics. For SMRs, small-core configurations and novel control schemes mean that dedicated mock-up tests should be planned, e.g. scaled critical assemblies or start-up measurements on prototype units. Advanced Gen-IV designs also need target data: for example, pebble-bed reactors require diffusion-length and spectral experiments in graphite, molten salt reactors (MSR) need in-situ thermal scattering measurements for circulating fuel, and lead-cooled fast reactors need lead- or LBE-reflector benchmarks.

Recognizing the gaps, international agencies are extending multi-physics benchmarks: NEA urges matching key experimental needs with existing and/or planned facilities for new systems. IAEA's Coordinated Research Project on coupled neutronics/thermal-hydraulics for research reactors also underscores this trend: it will develop both computational and experimental benchmarks for advanced coupled analysis [41]. In practice, designers of SMRs and Gen-IV systems should plan zero-power mockups or pulse-reactor tests of their core concepts (flux distribution, reactivity coefficients, kinetics) early in development. Long-term operation goals (flexible load-following, lifespan extension) also drive experiments on fuel aging (radiation damage effects on neutronics), which tie back to irradiation tests in materials research reactors.

Overall, new reactor designs represent an inherently forward-looking category of experimental needs. They expand capabilities beyond those of existing fleets, open new technical and industrial possibilities, and support transformative goals such as waste minimization and eventual fuel-cycle closure. As such, they require a coordinated, sustained experimental program capable of generating both clean integral data and high-fidelity multiphysics benchmarks.

Table III. Non-exhaustive list of experiments for new reactor designs. Tiers: optimizing, enabling, transformative. Difficulty: low, medium, high, very high. Bold: reactor facility required. [34], [42]–[47]

Experiment / Facility Type	Purpose / Application	Target metric (examples)	Tier	Diff.
Fast-spectrum critical assemblies (BFS, ZPR-6/7, ZEBRA, MASURCA)	Core physics validation for SFR/LFR: k_{eff} , β_{eff} , sodium void, control worth	k_{eff} unc. ≤ 300 pcm for design (IRPhEP); β_{eff} unc. 3-5% typical for ZPR evaluations	E/T	H
Sodium void worth tests (MASURCA, BFS)	Validate SVW reactivity feedback coefficients	SVW unc. $\leq 10\%$ (IRPhEP SFR benchmark, no lower bound)	E/T	VH
Control rod worth & absorber material experiments	Safety shutdown margin for fast reactors	Unc. $\leq 5\%$ for integral worths (IRPhEP)	E/T	H
Lead(-bismuth) reflector /void experiments (LFR/ADS environments, MYRRHA, ALFRED)	Validate LBE scattering, heat removal coupling, spectral hardening	k_{eff} sensitivity to reflector unc. ≤ 200 pcm (RELAP5 + ERANOS validation)	E/T	M
Molten salt reactor salt-physics exp. (β_{eff}, density, temp. coeff.)	Validate reactivity feedback in circulating fuel	Typical precision 1-2% for salt density, temp. coefficients	E/T	M
HTGR graphite irradiation & feedback experiments	Cross-sections, moderator temperature coefficient	Graphite heat capacity & Wigner-energy unc. $\leq 3\%$ (Petten graphite)	E/T	M
High-fidelity core mapping (flux, fission rate, spectrum)	Multiphys. & validation for f/t advanced designs [48]–[50]	Spectral index unc. $\leq 5\%$ (IRPhEP)	E/T	M
Transient experiments (UO_2, MOX, metallic fuels)	LOF/LOHS/UTOP transient behavior for advanced SFR/LFR	Fuel enthalpy-to-failure unc. $\leq 10\%$ (TREAT)	E/T	VH
TH + neutronics coupled integral tests (e.g., Phénix end-of-life tests)	Multiphysics validation for large-core SFR/LFR	Power distribution benchmarks: unc. $\leq 5\%$	E/T	VH

2.4. Education and training

This experimental domain is enabling in a human and institutional sense: without sustained hands-on training, operational literacy, and shared experimental benchmarks, even the most advanced digital models lose their interpretive context. Practical experimentation remains essential for cultivating the intuition, judgment, and cross-disciplinary fluency required in reactor physics. It serves all three major societal objectives:

- Safety and competence preservation: life-extension programs depend on operators, engineers, and analysts who understand the physical basis of reactivity, feedback, and measurement, not only through simulations but through direct experience.
- Innovation continuity: fuel-cycle development and new-reactor concepts require experimentalists who can design, execute, and interpret measurements. Without such expertise, advanced systems remain theoretical
- Sustainability and equity: distributed, accessible facilities align with Schumacher’s appropriate technology and Illich’s convivial tools ideas.

The technical difficulty of education-oriented experiments is generally low to moderate, but their strategic importance is exceptionally high. They ensure the renewal of the nuclear profession, maintaining a living, practiced knowledge base rather than one that is merely archived or simulated. The principal challenge is not technical but structural: securing sustained institutional, political, and academic support. Without clear recognition of their value, university-scale reactors and experimental benches face chronic resource limitations; precisely when global nuclear expansion demands the largest cohort of trained professionals in decades [51], [52].

Table IV. Non-exhaustive list of experiments of interest for education and training. Tiers: optimizing, enabling, transformative. Difficulty: low, medium, high, very high. Bold: reactor facility required.

Experiment / Facility Type	Purpose / Application	Tier	Diff.
Zero-Power Teaching & Research Reactors (CROCUS, AKR-2, VR-1)	Provide hands-on neutronics training; maintain practical understanding of core physics and safety	E	L/M
Instrumentation & Detector Training Benches	Teach measurement principles, data acquisition, and uncertainty treatment	E	L
Integrated Neutronics/ Thermal-Hydraulics Student Experiments	Foster systems thinking, multiphysics interpretation, and validation culture	E	M
Digital Twin and Virtual Experiment Platforms	Maintain training capacity where reactors unavailable; enable global access	O	L
International Student & Researcher Mobility Programs (ENEN, IAEA NKM and RRRS, NEA NEST)	Sustain workforce pipeline and shared competence across generations	E	M
Facility-based Joint Experiments (IAEA)	Strengthen international harmonization of measurements and uncertainty	E	M

3. APPLICATION CASE: A TEACHING & RESEARCH FAST ZERO-POWER REACTOR

Despite renewed interest in nuclear energy, no dedicated fast-spectrum breeder or burner reactor is currently operating as a full demonstration facility. The WPRS Zero-Power Reactor Task Force [5] documents this decline: since 2000, over 15 experimental fast reactors have been shut down or restricted in scope (EBR-II, FFTF, Dounreay, Phénix, Masurca) with the notable exception of VENUS at SCK CEN [53], [54]. Recent attempts to revive a European fast-spectrum zero-power capability, such as the ZEPHYR project [47], illustrate both the recognized need and the difficulty of re-establishing such infrastructure. As a consequence, the international community faces a structural bottleneck: there is little to no modern, flexible, academically accessible fast-spectrum facility to train students, qualify instrumentation, or perform the integral experiments needed for fuel-cycle closure, advanced reactors, and nuclear-data validation – precisely the needs identified in Sections 2.2–2.4.

At EPFL, CROCUS provides an exceptionally effective platform for education and research in reactor physics: safe, flexible, inexpensive to operate, and ideal for hands-on teaching [55]–[57]. However, as a light-water moderated system, it necessarily anchors teaching and research activities in the thermal-neutron paradigm. This shapes not only experimental programs but also transmitted intuition: students "think in thermal neutrons", detectors are optimized for that range, and validation work gravitates toward thermal spectra. Yet the needs identified in Sections 2.2–2.4 all show critical and increasing demand for fast-spectrum expertise.

A fast-spectrum university ZPR would not replicate industrial reactors, nor replace national laboratories. Instead, it would fill the exact gap highlighted by WPRS and WPEC: small, flexible, academically operated integral facilities capable of generating clean, well-characterized, low-uncertainty data. Such a facility would:

- Educate a new generation of fast-reactor scientists: students would gain hands-on experience with fast-spectrum kinetics, shielding, dosimetry, detection, reactivity control, and safety-skills that do not develop naturally in thermal-only training.
- Enable critical fast-spectrum integral experiments: this includes reaction-rate distributions, spectral indices, sodium-void coefficients (if designed accordingly), control-rod worth experiments, and benchmark lattices for SFR/ADS validation.

- Provide an accessible platform for fast-spectrum instrumentation R&D: fission chambers, rhodium/vanadium detectors, compact gamma thermometers, neutron flux monitors, and subcritical reactivity measurement techniques (e.g., source-jerk, noise methods).
- Support nuclear-data improvement: WPEC Subgroups repeatedly identify the lack of clean fast-spectrum integral data as a bottleneck for improving actinide and structural-material cross-sections. A fast ZPR could host targeted benchmark configurations directly aligned with the HPRL.
- Contribute to fuel-cycle closure: validating transmutation chains requires both differential (nuclear data) and integral (benchmark) experiments in representative fast spectra. A fast ZPR is the missing element between small differential installations and large irradiation facilities.
- Strengthen Switzerland's and Europe's sovereignty in nuclear expertise: without fast-spectrum training, Europe risks depending on foreign facilities for its long-term energy strategy, both for data and for expertise and know-how.

Overall, a teaching and research fast zero-power reactor would be a small-scale investment with disproportionate scientific and societal return: addressing critical gaps in training, validation, and innovation, while enabling Europe to build a fast spectrum knowledge base and ensure its long-term energy security.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Reactor physics relies fundamentally on studying, using, and developing reactor systems that are representative of present and future technologies. The analysis presented here shows that the need for experiments is clear and persistent: accurate nuclear data, high-quality benchmarks, validated simulation tools, and well-trained scientists capable of operating across the thermal and fast neutron spectra. These needs are not theoretical: they directly condition the feasibility of long-term operation, fuel-cycle closure, advanced reactor deployment, and Europe's capacity to innovate.

The cost of experimental infrastructure varies widely, and universities, ministries, national laboratories, and industrial partners each face different constraints. Experimental reactors and mock-ups are often viewed by industry primarily as an operational cost or even a liability, rather than a strategic asset, whereas academic and governmental actors tend to see them as long-term enablers. Yet the evidence presented here shows that the value of experiments extends far beyond short-term project needs: they underpin licensing credibility, long-term safety, supply-chain sovereignty, and workforce development. For each application class, concrete experiment types are identified that address recognized gaps and provide high leverage for system deployment and long-term sustainability.

A diversity of facilities would significantly accelerate the deployment of nuclear power by enabling both education and the generation of essential validation data. While universities can supply exploration, valuable data and training, large mock-ups fall under the incomparable capabilities of national laboratories. Following this reasoning, a fast zero-power reactor is under consideration at EPFL to complement CROCUS, fill critical fast-spectrum gaps identified by WPRS [5] and WPEC [2]–[4] and to contribute to the broader experimental landscape.

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